

The influence of company sourcing patterns on the adoption and effectiveness of zero-deforestation commitments in Brazil's soy supply chain

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ABSTRACT

Many companies sourcing agricultural commodities with high deforestation risk have committed to zero deforestation, meaning they intend to eliminate deforestation from their supply chains. While previous research has attempted to assess progress against such initiatives, little is known about how the characteristics of sourcing patterns may influence the adoption and potential effectiveness of zero-deforestation commitments. Supply chain stickiness – here defined as the geographic persistence in trade relationships between traders and sourcing regions over time – may reflect lock-in effects and the level of trust between the parties involved. Here, we use a metric of supply chain stickiness, calculated from temporal network analyses on the Brazilian soy export supply chain, as a proxy for these underlying dynamics to explore their effect on the adoption and effectiveness of zero deforestation commitments (ZDCs). Using data for 2004–2017, we find that although stickier traders are more likely to adopt ZDCs, they also appear to have less effective ZDCs than other traders (as indicated by the level of soy and territorial deforestation in their sourcing regions). This finding suggests that additional strategies are needed to increase the effectiveness of ZDCs.

1. Introduction

The international trade and consumption of agricultural commodities are estimated to drive around 26% of forest loss in the tropics and sub-tropics (Pendrill et al., 2019). As a result, multiple agricultural supply chain actors have committed to eliminate or reduce deforestation from their supply chains, either through multi-stakeholder coalitions, such as the Amazon Soy Moratorium (ASM) or through unilateral zero-deforestation commitments (ZDCs) (Garrett et al., 2019; Lambin et al., 2018).

Recent advances in remote sensing (Curtis et al., 2018) and supply chain mapping (Godar et al., 2015; Trase, 2020a) have facilitated

empirical research on such initiatives' effectiveness. For example, zu Ermgassen et al. (2020) used spatial data on individual supply chains to monitor progress against ZDCs in the Brazilian soy export sector. While these studies inform on the overall effectiveness of ZDCs, they provide scant evidence on how different sourcing strategies and patterns influence this effectiveness. Sourcing strategies are the main lever through which traders of deforestation-risk commodities influence activities further upstream in the supply chain (Lyons-White and Knight, 2018). Therefore, a better understanding of how different sourcing strategies, as reflected in spatiotemporal sourcing patterns, could influence actions on the ground is needed to enhance the effectiveness of ZDCs.

A critical characteristic of supply chain sourcing patterns is the

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degree of geographic persistence in bilateral trade flows (Villoria and Hertel, 2011). Such persistence may have a considerable influence on traders' capacity to source deforestation-risk commodities compliant with their ZDCs (Reis et al., 2020; Garrett et al., 2019).

Patterns of trade persistence may result from traders' strategies but also other factors beyond their direct control. For example, at the country-to-country trade level, geographic distance between trading countries affects the persistence of bilateral trade flows as more distant countries tend to have less persistent bilateral flows (Disdier and Head, 2008). Additionally, larger economies tend to have more persistent linkages (Kepaptsoglou et al., 2010), as do those with greater openness or exposure to trade (Melitz, 2002), ethnic and post-colonial linkages and those with similar governance regimes (Yu 2010).

The above referenced studies have provided insights into why trade relationships persist at the country-to-country level. However, the factors determining the persistence of subnational trade relationships, i.e., between companies, producers and subnational jurisdictions, are less well known. Persistent subnational trade relationships are driven by both financial (e.g., transportation costs) and non-financial factors (e.g., levels of trust) that are hard to quantify and disentangle from each other. Key gaps remain in our understanding of how such unobserved drivers of persistent subnational trade relationships may influence sustainability outcomes.

We apprehend persistence in trade patterns through the notion of "stickiness", which is defined as "*the maintenance and recovery, over time and through shocks, of supply chains' geographic network configurations, i. e., the network of trade linkages and flows between specific places of production and consumption, and specific actors including producers, traders, retailers, and consumers*" (Reis et al., 2020).

At the subnational trade level, various non-financial factors may influence supply chain relationships' stickiness at the supply-side (between production places and traders), including the social structure of supply chains, and power dynamics, which can induce various forms of lock-in effects. The social structure of supply chains – i.e., the networks of social relations embedded in economies that determine the market structure – is influenced by the level of trust among supply chain actors and may make trade relationships more or less persistent over time (Uzzi, 1997; Krippner and Alvarez, 2007; Henderson et al., 2002; Bair, 2008; Polanyi, 1944; Granovetter, 1985).

In some circumstances, these social and power dynamics, as well as other factors including actors' past decisions that constrain their supply chain relationships, can result in lock-in effects, i.e., situations where negative feedbacks reinforce existing supply chain relationships. These can be (i) infrastructural (Vanloqueren and Baret, 2009; Payo et al., 2016), when physical facilities bind together different supply chain actors; (ii) financial, e.g., through the existence of credit mechanisms; (iii) technological, e.g., when one actor dominates and patents key technologies upon which other actors are dependent (Fares et al., 2012), (iv) institutional when governance systems and norms exist (e.g. the ASM); or (v) related to consumer preferences for a brand, product or ingredient transparency, origin or quality (Narasimhan et al., 2009; Akkermans, 2001).

The literature suggests that such non-financial factors are likely to influence the adoption (Gardner et al., 2019; Dauvergne and Lister, 2013; Thorlakson et al., 2018) and effectiveness of sustainability commitments by companies (Garrett et al., 2019; Lambin et al., 2018). First, lock-in effects due to social dependence, technology and investments, bind farmers and companies together in long and stable relationships, potentially leading to imbalances in market power relations (Narasimhan et al., 2009). In some markets, especially in buyer-driven supply chains, traders strive for more power imbalances in their supply chains to exert more control over their suppliers (Dauvergne and Lister, 2013). Committing to sustainability criteria that condition suppliers' practices can further increase buyer companies' supply chain power, lock-ins and market dominance (Bastos Lima and Persson, 2020; Heron et al., 2018). Reverse causality is also possible: companies that

are more dominant may be more likely to commit to sustainability criteria because they have the means to do so or the agency to influence actors upstream in the supply chain. Finally, different levels of trust or distrust may promote or hinder more effective engagement between companies and producers to implement sustainability criteria (Ghosh and Fedorowicz, 2008; Skandrani et al., 2011; Heron et al., 2018).

Given the above, it is plausible that such non-financial factors influence both the observed patterns of stickiness in supply chain relationships and the adoption and effectiveness of sustainability commitments. However, no datasets exist that measure these factors comprehensively over large supply chains in a way that would enable quantitative evaluation of their influence on the adoption and effectiveness of ZDCs. Here we use observed patterns of trade stickiness as a proxy for these different factors. We measure these stickiness patterns through temporal network analyses of traders' relationships with production locations to explore their combined effects on both ZDC adoption and effectiveness by traders in the Brazilian soy export supply chain.

We focus on the soy export sector in Brazil, given its importance in deforestation and the momentum of ZDCs in this sector. We use spatiotemporal data on supply chain stickiness from Reis et al. (2020) covering the years 2003 – 2017. Two distinct econometric models are employed to assess (i) whether and to what extent supply chain stickiness tends to increase the probability of adopting a ZDC, and (ii) how supply chain stickiness may influence the overall effectiveness of ZDCs, measured through observed reductions of native vegetation loss in sourcing regions for companies with or without commitments. We highlight that our objective is not to assess the effectiveness of the ASMs or individual company's ZDCs according to their own definitions of forest and deforestation. As these definitions are heterogeneous, sometimes unclear or ambiguous, and temporally changing (zu Ermgassen et al., 2020; Leijten et al., 2020), this would essentially preclude any meaningful and statistically robust analysis. We rather build on a standardized and well-accepted definition of deforestation and native vegetation conversion in Brazil (see Trase, 2020b). By doing so, our assessment of ZDC effectiveness encompasses not only the aspects of implementation but also the design of these policies.

Through our empirical analysis, we seek to test two hypotheses:

1. Supply chain stickiness tends to increase the probability of adopting a ZDC, as stickier companies are more likely to have lock-ins, trust and power over a market, suggesting they also have the capacity to commit to sustainability.
2. The stickiness of different traders influences their effectiveness in implementing their ZDCs, through their capacity to influence their upstream supply chain, thus potentially reducing overall deforestation.

2. Methodology

To explore how the level of stickiness may influence the adoption and effectiveness of ZDCs within the Brazilian soy export sector, we used a panel data set with observations for all 1599 traders involved in the export of Brazilian soy during the years 2004 – 2017. These data control for mergers and acquisitions during the period 2004 – 2017. Below, we first describe how we compiled and processed these data (Section 2.1). After that, we describe the methods used to estimate the effect of stickiness on the adoption (Section 2.2) and effectiveness (2.3) of ZDCs.

2.1. Data

We obtained time-varying data on the level of stickiness for each of the 1599 traders from Reis et al. (2020). These data are based on the topological overlap metric used in network analysis. This metric captures the supply network configuration changes over time around a specific trader (given the municipalities from which they source in a

certain year) and ranges from 0% to 100%. Stickiness levels of 0% would indicate a complete change in a specific trader’s supply chain configuration in two consecutive years (the minimum time step needed to detect changes given available data). In contrast, stickiness levels of 100% would indicate complete persistence in the supply chain configuration. Fig. 1 in the supplementary material plots the general trend in stickiness between 2004 and 2017 in the Brazilian soy supply chain. To examine how different levels of stickiness may influence the effectiveness of ZDCs, we focus on two outcome variables believed to be directly related to the effectiveness of ZDCs: the level of soy deforestation risk and territorial deforestation allocated to individual traders (Trase, 2020b). Soy deforestation risk refers to the annual area of soy expansion (in hectares) within areas that have been deforested in the previous five years. Risk refers to the way this deforestation is allocated to the actors (here traders) along the supply chain, which is in proportion to the volume of soy that they export from a given municipality, relative to the total production of soy (by all producers) in the same municipality (Trase, 2020c, note that supply chain data at the submunicipal level are not available). Territorial deforestation differs from soy-deforestation in that it captures all deforestation from a municipality in the soy supply chain, regardless of whether it is linked to the direct expansion of soy or not (Trase, 2020c). Although this could mean that some territorial deforestation cannot be directly linked to the expansion of soy, it arguably provides a more accurate indication of the overall effectiveness of ZDCs, as it also partially accounts for indirect deforestation (Golnow et al., 2018). We sourced data on both types of deforestation risks from (Trase, 2020b,c) and zu Ermgassen et al. (2020). Deforestation includes any conversion of native vegetation within the Amazon, Cerrado and Pantanal biomes. We provide a sensitivity analysis towards forest definition choice in the Supplementary Material. Fig. 1 plots the aggregated annual level of both soy deforestation and territorial deforestation between 2004 and 2017. As the empirical relationships between stickiness and the adoption and effectiveness of ZDCs may be confounded by other variables, we sought to control for these variables in our multivariate regression analysis (see Sections 2.2 and 2.3). Table 1 lists all variables (i.e., both the variables of interest and control variables) used in the analysis, including their types and sources.

2.2. The influence of stickiness on the adoption of ZDC

To explore how the probability of adopting a ZDC may depend on the company-specific level of stickiness, we estimated several logistic regression models using the variables listed in Table 1, with the adoption of a ZDC in a particular year as the dependent binary variable. As traders can only once commit to zero deforestation, we set traders’ observations after the first year of the announcement to missing, as recommended by

Fig. 1. Time series plot showing the total level of soy deforestation and territorial deforestation in Brazil’s soy sourcing regions, after aggregating the data for all 1599 traders. Soy deforestation levels are not available for the years 2004 and 2005.

Table 1

Variables used in the multivariate regression analysis. All variables are attributed to companies.

Variable	Type	Source
<i>Variables of interest:</i>		
Adoption of zero-deforestation commitment	Binary (0/1)	zu Ermgassen et al. (2020)
Soy deforestation risk (Kha)	Continuous	Trase (2020c) and zu Ermgassen et al. (2020)
Supply chain stickiness (unitless)	Continuous	Reis et al. (2020)
Territorial deforestation risk (Kha)	Continuous	Trase (2020c) and zu Ermgassen et al. (2020)
<i>Control variables:</i>		
Export share (company’s export relative to total exports) (percentage)	Continuous	Trase (2020c)
Exports to Asian markets (company’s export to Asian markets relative to company’s total exports) (percentage)	Continuous	Trase (2020c)
Exports to European markets (company’s export to European markets relative to company’s total exports) (percentage)	Continuous	Trase (2020c)
Total unprotected area suitable for soy in sourcing region (ha)	Continuous	FUNAI (2020), ICMBio (2020), INCRA (2020), GeoLab - USP (2017)

McGrath (2015). In all models, we controlled for each trader’s export share within a given year and the share of exports going to the two most important export markets (Asia and Europe). As companies may be triggered to adopt ZDCs in response to increases in overall deforestation risk (Rueda et al., 2017), we also controlled for the level of territorial deforestation risk in the previous year. To account for time-invariant heterogeneity across traders (e.g. stemming from different attitudes toward environmental management practices; see Ho and Lin, 2012), we used a weighted demeaning approach that enabled us to explicitly estimate trader-specific fixed effects, implemented in the ‘alpaca’ package in R version 4.02 (R Core Team, 2020; Stammann, 2017). Although this approach could lead to biased estimates if the number of traders with commitments is large relative to the number of years – a statistical phenomenon known as the incidental parameters problem (Neyman and Scott, 1948; Lancaster, 2000) – this was not a concern in our case given that only 22 traders in our dataset have adopted ZDCs (which, when taken in aggregate, account for 78% of all soy exports between 2004 and 2017). Formally, we estimated the following model:

$$\ln\left(\frac{P_{i,t}}{1 - P_{i,t}}\right) = \alpha_i + \beta_1 stickiness_{i,t} + \sum_{k=1}^K \omega_k x_{k,i,t}, \tag{1}$$

where $P_{i,t}$ denotes the probability that trader i adopts a ZDC in year t (where ZDC can either refer to an individual ZDC or a ZDC adopted as part of the ASM), $stickiness_{i,t}$ denotes the level of stickiness, $x_{k,i,t}$ is a control variable (see Table 1), and α_i, β_1 and $\omega_1, \dots, \omega_K$ are parameters to be estimated. This equation resulted in 3 different regression models: one for all ZDCs, one for just the ASM and one for unilateral commitments.

Given the low number of traders with ZDCs, we did not account for year-specific fixed effects and the unprotected area suitable for soy as this would overfit the model (Hawkins, 2004). As the number of traders with unilateral commitments (i.e., commitments that are not part of the ASM) is even lower ($n = 5$), we set the third model’s positive convergence tolerance to 0.2, thus ensuring convergence (see McCullough, 2009 for further details). To assess the overall effect of stickiness on the probability of adopting a ZDC, we used all three models’ parameter estimates to compute the Average Marginal Effect (AME; Hilbe, 2009) of stickiness. Although it is plausible that the adoption of a ZDC also affects

levels of stickiness in consecutive years (i.e., reverse causality), we circumvented the issue by setting all consecutive observations to missing.

2.3. The moderating effect of stickiness on the effectiveness of ZDCs

Having assessed the effect of stickiness on the adoption of ZDCs, we examined how stickiness could moderate the effectiveness of soy ZDCs in reducing deforestation in Brazil. We estimated several regression models specifying how stickiness may amplify or repress the effect of ZDCs on soy deforestation and territorial deforestation, holding other things constant. As both dependent variables follow a heavily skewed distribution with many observations equal to 0, we used a negative binomial regression model. As opposed to the linear regression model, the negative binomial regression model’s underlying probability density function is more suited for modelling non-negative distributions clustered around 0 (Hilbe, 2011). Although the Poisson regression model may also be used for modelling such zero-inflated variables, it imposes the restrictive assumption that the mean and variance of the dependent variable are equal, which does not hold for our data. In the absence of publicly available information on the intended time schedules of all individual zero-deforestation commitments (Garrett et al., 2019), we arbitrarily assumed an implementation deadline of 2 years for all traders after the commitment was announced (after which a ZDC is expected to become effective). As a sensitivity test, we also consider an alternative implementation deadline of 5 years. To explicitly estimate the trader-specific fixed effects in a computationally efficient way, we used the *fixest* package in R version 4.0.2 (Bergé, 2020; R Core Team, 2020). The underlying algorithm replicates the results of an unconditional negative binomial fixed effects model with no downward bias in the standard errors (Bergé, 2018; Allison and Waterman, 2002). This measure enabled us to estimate the following equation:

$$Def_{i,t} = \exp(\alpha_i + \beta ZDC_{i,t} + \phi stickiness_{i,t} + \delta ZDC_{i,t-2} * stickiness_{i,t} + \sum_{k=1}^K \omega_k x_{k,i,t} + \gamma_t), \tag{2}$$

where $Def_{i,t}$ refers to either the annual level of soy risk or territorial deforestation for trader i in year t , $ZDC_{i,t-2}$ is a dummy (binary) variable denoting whether trader i has adopted a commitment in the 2 years preceding year t , $stickiness_{i,t}$ refers to the level of stickiness (rescaled to the unit interval to address overdispersion), $x_{k,i,t}$ is a control variable (see Table 1), and $\alpha_i, \phi, \beta, \delta, \gamma_t$ and $\omega_1, \dots, \omega_K$ are parameters to be estimated. To explore the sensitivity of our results to the choice of forest definition, we re-estimated Eq. (1) after excluding sourcing areas outside the Amazon biome, as these may not be considered forest according to some definitions (Leijten et al., 2020).

To gauge the moderating effect of stickiness on the effectiveness of ZDCs, we used the results of our regression estimates to predict, for each company that has adopted a commitment, what the effect of ZDCs would have been in the absence of an interaction effect. In other words, we compared the outcomes of a scenario that assumes no interaction between stickiness (i.e., $\delta = 0$) and the effectiveness of ZDCs with a scenario that does account for interaction (i.e., $\delta \neq 0$). To explore our estimates’ uncertainty, we drew on the variance-covariance matrix of the parameter estimates and ran 1000 Monte Carlo simulations, thereby following (Heilmayr et al., 2020a).

3. Results

3.1. The influence of stickiness on the adoption of ZDCs

Table 2 reports the regression estimates of Eq. (1). The first column shows the results for all ZDCs, while the second and third columns show separate regression estimates for the ASM (column 2) and unilateral commitments (column 3). Due to the small number of companies with ZDCs ($n = 22$, which nevertheless account for 78% of all soy exports),

Table 2
Logistic regression estimates of the probability of adopting a ZDC. Heteroskedasticity robust (White-Huber) standard errors in parentheses. Asterisks indicate the level of statistical significance ($p < 0.10$, $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$). AIC denotes Akaike information criterion and BIC denotes Bayesian information criterion.

	All commitments	Amazon Soy Moratorium	Unilateral Commitments
Stickiness (%)	0.05 * (0.03)	0.05 (0.03)	0.13 * ** (0.03)
Territorial deforestation (1-year lag)	0.02 (0.02)	0.01 (0.02)	0.09 * ** (0.02)
Export share (%)	0.04 (0.26)	0.05 (0.26)	-0.73 * ** (0.26)
Destination - Europe (%)	0.58 * (0.29)	0.56 * (0.28)	-0.04 (0.03)
Destination - Asia (%)	0.60 * (0.29)	0.58 * (0.27)	0.04 * ** (0.01)
McFadden’s Pseudo R ²	0.34	0.28	0.61
Observations	104	92	61
Trader fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year fixed effects	No	No	No
AIC	125.35	123.15	33.55
BIC	196.75	188.71	124.54
Log Likelihood	-35.67	-35.57	-6.77

the sample size reduces to 104 observations in model 1. The results in column 1 indicate that stickiness has a positive and significant effect on the adoption of ZDCs ($P < 0.05$) in the consecutive year, other things being equal. More specifically, the results from column 1 suggest that a one percentage point increase in stickiness increases the odds of adopting a ZDC by 5% ($\exp(0.05) \approx 1.05$). We obtained the same result when focussing only on the Amazon Soy Moratorium (second column, first row; $P < 0.1$). However, stickiness appears to have a stronger effect on the adoption of unilateral commitments ($P < 0.001$): a one-percentage-point increase in stickiness increases the odds of adopting a unilateral ZDC by 14% ($\exp(0.13) \approx 1.14$).

Fig. 2 plots the Average Marginal Effect (AME) of stickiness on the probability of adopting a ZDC. The top row of Fig. 2 indicates that on average, the probability of adopting a ZDC increases by 0.6% if stickiness increases by one percentage-point. Similar results are obtained when focussing only on the ASM (second row) or on unilateral commitments (third row).

3.2. The moderating effect of stickiness on the effectiveness of ZDCs

We report the regression estimates of Eq. (2) in Table 3. The first two columns show a positive and statistically significant relationship

Fig. 2. Average Marginal Effect (AME) of stickiness on the probability of adopting a ZDC, thereby distinguishing between commitments made as part of the Amazon Soy Moratorium (ASM; second row) and unilateral commitments (third row). Error bars denote 95% confidence intervals. Confidence intervals that do not contain the number 0 (here indicated by the dotted vertical line) are statistically different from 0.

Table 3

Negative binomial regression estimates of the annual amount of soy deforestation risk and territorial deforestation. Columns (1) and (3) assume a ZDC implementation deadline of 2 years, while columns (2) and (4) assume an implementation deadline of 5 years. Heteroskedasticity robust (White-Huber) standard errors in parentheses. Asterisks indicate the level of statistical significance ($p < 0.10$, $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$). Soy and territorial deforestation are represented in kha.

	Soy deforestation risk	Soy deforestation risk	Territorial deforestation	Territorial deforestation
Stickiness (0 –1)	0.60 ** (0.22)	0.63 ** (0.23)	0.13 (0.20)	0.11 (0.20)
Commitment (2-year lag)	0.06 (1.18)		0.69 (0.51)	
Stickiness x Commitment (2-year lag)	0.30 (1.32)		1.23 * (0.61)	
Commitment (5-year lag)		0.79 (1.00)		-0.34 (0.79)
Stickiness x Commitment (5-year lag)		-1.57 (1.22)		1.98 * (0.89)
Export share (%)	0.29 ** (0.09)	0.24 * (0.10)	0.16 * (0.06)	0.20 ** (0.07)
Destination - Europe (%)	0.05 ** (0.01)	0.05 ** (0.01)	0.06 ** (0.00)	0.06 ** (0.00)
Destination - Asia (%)	0.05 ** (0.00)	0.05 ** (0.00)	0.06 ** (0.00)	0.06 ** (0.00)
Unprotected suitable forest area	0.48 * (0.22)	0.52 * (0.24)	0.42 * (0.21)	0.53 * (0.23)
Theta (overdispersion)	1.17 ** (0.18)	1.20 ** (0.19)	0.99 ** (0.11)	0.96 ** (0.11)
McFadden's Pseudo R ²	0.61	0.61	0.60	0.60
Observations	4692	4692	7168	7168
Trader fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
AIC	1980.98	1978.99	2994.98	3003.94
BIC	4626.96	4624.97	6660.63	6669.59
Log Likelihood	-580.49	-579.49	-964.49	-968.97

Fig. 3. Notched box plots showing the results of 1000 Monte Carlo simulations of the effects of ZDCs – with and without an interaction effect with stickiness – on soy deforestation and territorial deforestation. Median estimates – including their confidence intervals – are indicated by the notches in each plot. Upper hinges represent 75% quantiles, and lower hinges represent 25% quantile. Upper (lower) whiskers represent the largest outcomes that are less than or equal to upper (lower) hinge * the interquartile range.

between stickiness and soy deforestation (first row, $P < 0.01$). Conversely, there is no statistically significant relationship between stickiness and territorial deforestation, as shown in columns (3) and (4). In addition, there is no relationship between the adoption of ZDCs and soy deforestation or territorial deforestation, regardless of whether a 2-year (third row) or 5-year lag (fourth row) is assumed. However, the third and fourth columns indicate a positive interaction effect between stickiness and the adoption of ZDCs on territorial deforestation ($P < 0.05$, regardless of the choice of implementation deadline), suggesting that stickiness may hamper the effectiveness of ZDCs. These results remain robust when focussing only on deforestation in the Amazon biome (see [Table 1 of the supplementary material](#)).

To examine the magnitude of this interaction effect (in kha) as well as the underlying uncertainty, [Fig. 3](#) shows the results of the Monte-Carlo simulation. Each of the four notched boxplots compares the results of 1000 simulations with and without an interaction effect on the total level of soy deforestation (top row) and territorial deforestation (bottom row). Given the uncertainty regarding the implementation deadline of ZDCs, boxplots in the left column account for an implementation period of 2 years, and boxplots on the right account for an implementation period of 5 years. The boxes display the interquartile range (25–75 th percentile) of all 1000 simulations' outcomes. The notches show the 95% confidence interval around the median (see [McGill et al., 1978](#) for a more detailed explanation of notched box plots). Most simulations confirm that the interaction effect of stickiness and ZDCs tends to result in more soy deforestation and territorial deforestation, with none of the notches overlapping. By way of example, the top-left plot shows that the median estimate of the effect of ZDCs on soy deforestation increases from 28 (6–49) to 738 (697–778) kha if there is an interaction effect between stickiness and ZDCs. These findings suggest that traders with higher stickiness are less likely to effectively implement their ZDCs than traders with lower stickiness. However, even in the absence of an interaction effect, most simulations still show a positive effect of ZDCs on soy deforestation and territorial deforestation, suggesting that notwithstanding the level of stickiness, additional efforts are needed to implement ZDCs.

4. Discussion

We find that stickiness tends to increase the probability of adopting a ZDC in the consecutive year, supporting our first hypothesis that stickier companies are more likely to have lock-ins, trust, and bargaining power. A potential explanation for this is that stickier traders deliberately aim for stable trade relations with certain geographical regions and committing to zero-deforestation can be a strategy to reduce the risk of supply disruptions ([Rueda et al., 2017](#)). Additionally, sticky traders may also be more vulnerable than volatile traders to reputational damage if their suppliers are brought into disrepute, which may incentivise sticky traders to adopt ZDCs ([Tamayo-Torres et al., 2019](#)). This explanation is consistent with the green club theory, which describes how reputational risk aversion may trigger firms to participate in 'green clubs' ([Barnett and Hoffman, 2008](#); [Potoski and Prakash, 2013](#)).

Despite the presumed positive influence of stickiness on the adoption of ZDCs, we also found strong evidence that stickiness tends to increase the risk of soy-deforestation, supporting our second hypothesis on the *link* between stickiness and effectiveness of commitments. Moreover, traders committed to zero-deforestation with higher levels of stickiness also show higher risks of territorial deforestation. Both findings suggest that stickiness may undermine the implementation and overall effectiveness of ZDCs at the traders' level. An explanation could be that sticky traders drive continued demand for soy from certain regions, which may send encouraging signals to actors on the ground to expand production ([Richards et al., 2012](#)). Moreover, stickiness may also give rise to lock-in effects where traders become dependent on certain suppliers, thus hindering traders from switching to producers complying with ZDC-criteria ([Schmitz et al., 2016](#)). Effectiveness of ZDCs could in some cases be

further undermined if the adoption of ZDCs leads to a situation where producers continue to deforest to produce soy, whilst selling to intermediaries instead of through direct contracts ([Meyfroidt et al., 2018](#), [Alix-Garcia and Gibbs, 2017](#), [Carvalho et al., 2019](#)).

Conversely, low-stickiness traders may more easily achieve a ZDC, but if only by switching to low-deforestation sourcing regions, this may not necessarily contribute to more effective deforestation reduction on the ground. We highlight that we did not find any evidence that the ZDCs reduce native vegetation loss, regardless of the level of stickiness. This finding is consistent with recent literature for individual ZDCs ([zu Ermgassen et al., 2020](#)). In contrast, for the ASM as a collective ZDC, the literature shows it effectively reduces deforestation ([Heilmayr et al., 2020b](#)). These two studies nuance the interpretation that stickiness is indeed thwarting the effectiveness of ZDCs, as it could also be that at the end of our study period (i.e., the year 2017), no action had been taken yet to implement the individual commitments.

A limitation of our study is that, as explained in the introduction, our stickiness metric captures and reflects several underlying dynamics, including lock-in effects, trust, and certain power dynamics. Thus, the data do not allow us to identify which of these factors are more influential in the adoption and effectiveness of ZDCs. Whilst there are reasons to believe that stickiness is a useful proxy for these value chain dynamics, additional data are required to attribute the overall effect of stickiness to these underlying factors. These factors may influence ZDC adoption and effectiveness in different, contradictory ways. Furthermore, due to the small number of traders with zero-deforestation commitments in our sample, our analysis may suffer from a lack of statistical power, potentially resulting in type II errors, i.e., failing to identify certain statistical significance effects that are occurring. Moreover, given that the supply chain data are aggregated at the municipality level, it is conceivable that our conclusions do not hold at the property level (an example of the ecological inference problem; [Freedman et al., 1998](#)). Yet, assessing ZDC at municipality level allows to account for local spillovers and thus measures ZDC's effectiveness at jurisdictional level beyond the specific sourcing farms ([Leijten et al., 2021](#); [Godar et al., 2016](#)). Further research could explore the extent to which our qualitative conclusions hold in other supply chains or at more disaggregated levels, assuming future data availability. Despite these limitations, our study contributes to a burgeoning empirical literature on the effectiveness of zero-deforestation commitments ([Bager and Lambin, 2020](#); [Moffette and Gibbs, 2019](#); [zu Ermgassen et al., 2020](#)). Our study builds on this work by highlighting the concept of stickiness as a potential proxy for unobserved value chain dynamics that may influence the adoption and effectiveness of ZDCs and other corporate sustainability initiatives. Whilst our findings suggest that stickiness incentivises traders operating in the Brazilian soy export sector to adopt ZDCs, they also show that, up until 2017, stickiness may have counteracted their effectiveness. This finding suggests that additional strategies, such as public-private partnerships ([Furumo and Lambin, 2020](#)), moratoria ([Soterroni et al., 2019](#)), certification schemes ([van der Ven et al., 2018](#)) and enhanced representation of upstream actors in ZDCs ([Virah-Sawmy et al., 2019](#)) may be needed to support the implementation of ZDCs and to eliminate deforestation.

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CRedit authorship Contribution Statement

Floris Leijten: Writing – original draft, preparation, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Tiago N.P. dos Reis:** Writing – original draft,

preparation, Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation. **Sarah Sim:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Peter H Verburg:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Patrick Meyfroidt:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.envsci.2021.10.032](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.10.032).

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